

Gold Nanoparticle modified PVA/GOx Biocomposite Membranes via Electrospun for Biosensor Applications

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Abstract

This study successfully combined the advantages of electrospun technology, gold nanoparticles and electrochemical biosensor to produce a high-sensitive glucose biosensor. We prepared the biocomposite electrospun nanofiber membranes by electrospun a solution of PVA, GOx and Gold nanoparticles. SEM image showed the membrane was a nanoporous structure; TEM image indicated that gold nanoparticles were well dispersed in nanofiber; The results of FT-IR showed that GOx exist in nanofibers. With the addition of gold nanoparticles, the sensitivity of PVA/GOx/Au fiber membrane was much higher than other samples, and the 50ppm of nanoparticles was the best proportion in this experiment.

1 Introduction

Electrospun technology is a manufacturing technique that extracts continuous fibers from polymer solutions or melts under a strong electrostatic field. The jet flow which is ejected from the tip of Taylor Cone can extend to a long distance, thereby obtaining a super-fine fiber. Fibers manufactured using this method possess smaller diameter, high specific surface area and great porosity. Due to these excellent properties, the fibers can be applied as filter material, biomedical applications, biosensors, photoelectric components, and reinforced composite materials [1]. Moreover, it is reported recently that the composite fabrics of drug carrier prepared by electrospun have chance of healing the retinal damage.

Biosensor is a device which is combined immobilized biorecognition element with transducer. It can monitor chemical substances on the inside or outside of organism by translating them into a transducer signal after a coupling of the biochemical

and transducer type reaction [2]. Glucose biosensor is an important development for biosensor, and it also has an extensive application from blood glucose sensor to food analysis. Then, the stability of enzymes is crucial for the fabrication of biosensors. A number of techniques have been used for the immobilization of enzymes on different substrates to improve the enzymatic activity and stability [3]. Poly (vinyl Alcohol) (PVA) is one of electrospun polymer materials because it has good hydrophilicity, high mechanical strength and flexibility. Recently, there were many systematic studies about the effect of molecular weight, the solution PH value and small molecule additives etc. on PVA electrospun behavior [4-6]. These studies have made the manufacturing method of PVA electrospinning nanofibers become developed. Besides, PVA has excellent film-forming and biocompatibility, and that is considered an appropriate matrix for enzyme immobilization [7]. The enzymes can be immobilized on PVA matrix by different methods (cross-linking with aromatic tri-isocyanates, gamma or UV irradiation etc.). However, because of the compaction and low-conductivity of the membrane, it is adverse for the substrate to infiltrate into the enzyme membrane and for the electrons to transfer between the enzyme membrane and the electrode[8]. Characteristics of gold nanoparticles such as high surface-to-volume ratio, high surface energy, ability to decrease distance between glucose oxidase (GOx) and electrode, and the functioning as electron-conducting pathways between redox protein and the electrode surface, have been claimed as reasons to facilitate electron transfer between GOx and electrode surfaces [9].

This study combined the advantage of electrospinning, gold nanoparticles and electrochemical biosensor in order to produce a high-sensitive glucose biosensor.

In electrospun technology, our laboratory had made a self-assembled electrospun device, and we also found the best electrospun parameter of PVA. We used the established electrospun technology and prepared PVA nanofiber membranes instead of traditional films, and we expect that nanoporous structure could improve the sensitivity of glucose biosensor. Moreover, we used the characteristics of gold nanoparticles to increase the efficiency of electron transfer.

2 Experimental

2.1 Material

Poly (vinyl Alcohol) with 98~99% hydrolyzed, and a molecular weight of 146,000-186,000 was purchased from Sigma-Aldrich. The concentration of the prepared PVA solution was 7wt%. Glucose oxidase (G7141, Sigma-Aldrich) was 153,100 units/G and solid. The disodium Hydrogen Phosphate 12-water (ECHO Chemical CO.) and Sodium Hydrogen Phosphate Dehydrate (ECHO Chemical CO.) were used for phosphate buffer solution. Dextrose Anhydrous (D(+)-Glucose) was purchased from ECHO Chemical Company. Gold nanoparticle solution with 10~100nm and 1000ppm was purchased from Lihochem Inc.

2.2 Preparation

PVA/GOx film: We dipped the Pt electrode in a 200U/ml PVA/GOx solution to form a coating film. After film-forming, the PVA/GOx film was cross-linked with glutaraldehyde solution.

PVA/GOx fiber: We prepared the biocomposite electrospun nanofiber membranes on the Pt electrode by electrospun a solution of PVA and GOx. After electrospun, the electrospun PVA/GOx nanofiber membranes were cross-linked with glutaraldehyde solution.

PVA/GOx/Au fiber: We prepared the biocomposite electrospun nanofiber membranes on the Pt electrode by electrospun a solution of PVA, GOx and gold nanoparticle solution. After electrospun, the electrospun PVA/GOx/Au nanofiber membranes were cross-linked with glutaraldehyde solution.

2.2 Electrospun

This experiment used a self-assembled electrospun device, as Fig.1 shown, and an injection spinneret (0.008ml/min) powered by a syringe pump (Model

101 Series, Kd scientific, USA). The syringe pump was connected to a Teflon tube and the tube was attached to a plain-stitch spinneret acting as the spinneret. An electrostatic controller (LGC-300 series, Taiwell, Taiwan) connected to the collector, and a ground wire connected to the spinneret. The applied voltage was 25KV, and the working distance was 18cm in the electrospinning system.

2.3 Analysis

The morphology of PVA/GOx film and PVA/GOx fiber was characterized by a variable vacuum scanning electronic microscope (VVSEM, S3000, Hitachi, Japan). The transmission electron microscopy (TEM) images were obtained by JEOL 200CX. The chemical composition was verified by Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR-8300, Shimadzu, Japan). The thickness of PVA/GOx film and PVA/GOx fiber was measured by alpha step (Surfcoder Model ET-3000, Kosaka Laboratory Ltd., Japan). The measurement was performed using a scan length of 1 mm, scan speed of 0.05 mm/sec, and stylus contact pressure of 5×10^{-7} kg.

2.4 Electrochemical Measurements

In this study, the electrochemical measurement of glucose biosensor was three-electrode system with potentiostat (CH Instruments Electrochemical Analyzer). Ag/AgCl was used as reference electrode was, and platinum foils were used as working electrode and counter electrode. The working potential was 0.8V. The PBS (phosphate buffered solution, 0.1M and PH6.8) is a buffer solution containing disodium hydrogen phosphate 12-water and sodium hydrogen phosphate dehydrate. All electrochemical reactions were in the solution.

3 Results and Discussion

3.1 The morphology of electrospun PVA/GOx fiber membrane

Fig.2 was the deposited configuration of electrospun PVA/GOx fiber membrane on Pt electrode. The electrospun PVA/GOx fiber formed a white micro-transparent membrane on Pt electrode. In order to examine the physical morphology of electrospun PVA/GOx fiber membrane, we must use SEM and TEM to observe the membrane.

Fig.3(a) showed the SEM image of PVA/GOx film. The coating film was compact, and it was not a

porosity structure. Fig.3(b) showed the SEM image of electrospun PVA/GOx fiber membrane, and the fiber diameter was $209\pm 35\text{nm}$. This structure of electrospun PVA/GOx fiber membrane was a nanoporous structure, and it would provide larger reaction area between glucose and enzyme.

The dispersion of Au nanoparticles within the electrospun PVA nanofibers was examined by TEM. AS shown as Fig.4, the gold nanoparticles were well dispersed in electrospun PVA nanofiber, forming a random distribution in the nanofiber.

3.2 Characteristics of Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy

We could examine whether GOx existed in the electrospun nanofibers by Fourier transform infrared (FT-IR) spectroscopy as shown as Fig.5. In the FT-IR spectrum of PVA (Fig.5 (a)), PVA exhibited stretching vibration band of hydrogen-bond alcohol (O - H) at about 3364 cm^{-1} . Because of the superposition of stretching vibration of O-H and N-H, the absorption peaks at 3348 cm^{-1} was wider than that of PVA in the FT-IR spectrum of electrospun PVA/GOx membrane and electrospun PVA/GOx/Au membrane (Fig.5(b) and (c)). Then we studied the absorption band from $700\text{ to }2000\text{ cm}^{-1}$ as shown as Fig.6. In the FT-IR spectrum of electrospun PVA/GOx membrane, electrospun PVA/GOx/Au membrane and GOx (Fig.6(b), (c) and (d)), we could see the characteristic absorption peaks at 1654 cm^{-1} , which were induced from O=C - NH of GOx; However, it didn't appear at 1654 cm^{-1} in the FT-IR spectrum of PVA (Fig.6(a)). The results were in agreement where GOx really exist in the electrospun nanofibers.

3.3 Sensitivity analysis

Fig.7 displayed the typical effect of addition of glucose concentration, where the current value rose with the glucose concentration. The range of concentration of glucose solution was 1 to 34 mM in this experiment. However, we had to determine the sensitivity of glucose biosensor from the slope of glucose concentration versus current value. Fig.8 was the resulting calibration curve of different samples. The current response increased linearly with glucose concentration at low concentration, and then it flowed by a slower and non-linear increases. As known, the blood glucose level of normal person

ranges from 4 to 6mM. The sensitivity of glucose biosensor ($\mu\text{A}/\text{mM}$) was the slope of the curve within 0 to 10mM of glucose concentration. From the slopes, we could obtain that the sensitivity of all samples as shown as table1. The sensitivities of PVA film and PVA/GOx fiber were 15.9 and 18.5 $\mu\text{A}/\text{mM}$. The sensitivity of PVA/GOx fiber was 1.1 times more than the other one. The thickness of the deposited nanofiber membrane was measured by alpha step as displayed in Fig. 9. The average thickness is approximate 15.8 and 13.4 μm for PVA casting film (a) and electrospun PVA nanofiber membrane (b), respectively. All the sample of electrospun nanofiber membranes had same thickness by controlling the electrospinning time. With greatest thickness of casting film, it could hold more GOx than electrospun nanofiber membranes, but the results of sensitivity proved the assumption wrong. It indicated the electrospinning were an effective method for enzyme immobilization because it could form a nanoporous structure with large specific surface area (as shown as Fig.3).

Besides, with the addition of gold nanoparticles, the sensitivity of PVA/GOx/Au fiber membrane was higher than the PVA/GOx fiber membrane. The sensitivity of PVA/GOx/Au-50ppm was $37.65\mu\text{A}/\text{mM}$, and it was 2.4 times more than PVA/GOx fiber membrane. However, above the proportion of 50ppm, the sensitivity didn't increase. Gold nanoparticles play a significant role in improving response performance of glucose sensing membranes. Firstly, the gold nanoparticles could absorb larger amount of enzyme molecules due to their high surface area and great surface energy. Therefore, the GOx could be immobilized firmly by gold nanoparticles [10]. Finally, the electron-transfer rate between redox protein and electrode surface is slow, and the PVA matrix is also a low-conductive material, they are the major barricades of the electrochemical system. The gold nanoparticles could absorb the hydrophilic oxidized flavin adenine dinucleotide (FAD) which is the active center of GOx molecule, so the gold nanoparticles act as direct-electron-transferring channels from the active center of GOx to electrode and facilitate the transfer of electrons.

3.4 Kinetic parameters

As shown as Fig.10, when the glucose concentration was high, the response current presented slow and

non-linear increase. These result showed the Michaelis - Menten dynamic characteristic. The apparent Michaelis-Menten constant (K_m^{app}) can be calculated from Hanes-Woolf regression[11] as follow:

$$\frac{S}{I} = \frac{1}{I_{max}} S + \frac{K_m^{app}}{I_{max}} \quad (1)$$

$$I_{max} = \frac{1}{\text{Slope}} \quad (2)$$

$$K_m^{app} = y - \text{intercept} \times I_{max} \quad (3)$$

where S is glucose concentration, I is the steady-state current, and I_{max} is the maximum current measured under saturated substrate condition. The K_m^{app} , which gives an indication of enzyme substrate kinetics for biosensor, was estimated base on the data obtained from the S/I vs. S curve as shown as Fig.10. The K_m^{app} value for an enzymatic reaction determines the affinity of the enzyme for the substrate, whereas the value of I_{max} provides the maximum rate of enzyme reaction when the enzyme is saturated by the substrate. And the smaller value of K_m^{app} indicates the increased affinity. The K_m^{app} of PVA/GOx fiber was 13.2mM, which was slight lower than PVA/GOx film. It revealed that the nanoporous structure of electrospun membrane was advantage for glucose to infiltrate into the enzyme membrane. Furthermore, the I_{max} of PVA/GOx/Au-50ppm fiber was 434.78 μ A, and K_m^{app} was 0.83mM, which was much lower than other samples. The lowest value of K_m^{app} indicated that the addition of gold nanoparticle could facilitate the electron-transfer efficiency and proposed immobilized enzymes shows higher biological affinity to glucose.

Conclusion

In this study, PVA/GOx/Au biocomposite nanofiber membranes were prepared by electrospun and applied in biosensor successfully. The SEM image indicated that the nanofiber membrane was a nanoporous structure with high specific surface area; The TEM image demonstrated that the locations of nanoparticles in nanofibers were scattered without reunion. The sensitivity of PVA/GOx fiber was 1.1 times more than PVA film because of its nanoporous structure and large specific surface area. Besides, with the addition of gold nanoparticles, the

sensitivity of PVA/GOx/Au-50ppm was 37.65 μ A/mM, and it was 2.4 times more than PVA/GOx fiber membrane; The I_{max} of PVA/GOx/Au-50ppm fiber was 434.78 μ A, and K_m^{app} was 0.83mM, which was much lower than other samples. Furthermore, the best proportion of nanoparticled was 50ppm, and above the proportion of 50ppm, the sensitivity didn't increase.

Table 1 The sensitivities and K_m^{app} of samples

	PVA/GOx/Au			
	100	50	5	1
Proportion (ppm)				
Sensitivity (μ A/mM)	37.24	37.65	24.72	21.56
K_m^{app} (mM)	1.63	0.83	7.77	10.41
I_{max} (μ A)	416.67	434.78	454.55	454.55
	PVA/GOx fiber	PVA/GOx film		
Sensitivity (μ A/mM)	18.49	15.94		
K_m^{app} (mM)	13.22	14.12		
I_{max} (μ A)	434.78	400.00		

Fig.1. The Schematic illustration of electrospun system.

Fig.2. The deposited configuration of electrospun PVA/GOx fiber membrane on Pt electrode

Fig.3. The SEM image of (a) PVA/GOx film and (b) electrospun PVA/GOx nanofiber membrane.

Fig.4. The TEM image of electrospun PVA/GOx/Au nanofiber membrane.

Fig.5. FT-IR spectrum of (a) PVA, (b) electrospun PVA/GOx nanofiber membrane, (c) electrospun PVA/GOx/Au nanofiber membrane and (d) GOx.

Fig.6. FT-IR spectrum of (a) PVA, (b) electrospun PVA/GOx nanofiber membrane, (c) electrospun PVA/GOx/Au nanofiber membrane and (d) GOx with absorption band from 700 to 2000 cm⁻¹.

Fig.7. The typical effect of addition of glucose concentration.

Fig.8. The calibration curve of samples.

Fig.9. Thickness profile of the deposited web in (a) PVA film and (b) electrospun PVA nanofiber membrane.

Fig.10. Hanes-Woolf Curve of electrospun PVA/GOx/Au-50ppm nanofiber membrane.

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